

Social

MOTIVATION OF STUDYING WITH THE HELP OF INFORMATION SYSTEMS

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Abstract

Information technology is widely used in the educational process. To increase the motivation for learning, various methodical methods and means are used. The experience of using the "matrix" information system shows how interest appears to the learning process and all its participants: teachers and students. The article is of interest to all participants of the educational process.

Keywords: Information Systems; Educational Process; Information Society; Computer Technologies.

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1. Introduction

Modern information technologies find the most diverse application in various subject areas of human activity [1, 2]. Education is such a field of human activity where the most advanced should be used: - the latest achievements of science and technology, both in the humanities and in natural disciplines and spheres of human activity [4, 5].

Information systems, computer technologies, social networks have recently covered many aspects of the life of civil society and offer new perspectives and opportunities for people. In education, distance technologies have recently begun to be used, gaming methods have helped to increase the interest of students and students to study, etc. [3, 7]

In the Graduate School of Press and Media Industry over the past few years, the information system, known as the "matrix," has been successfully applied.

The main goals and tasks that this information system solves: [9, 10]

- Increased interest in the learning process by both students and teachers;
- Motivation of students to monitor academic progress during the academic semester;
- Increase of control over students' progress on the part of teachers, department and dean's office;
- The validity of assessments of students' knowledge during the intermediate control of academic performance during the semester;
- The reasonableness of assessments of students' knowledge during the final control of students' knowledge at the end of the semester;
- Verification of students' knowledge of compliance with the declared competencies in the funds of evaluation tools developed by the teachers of the department in accordance with the curricula of the academic disciplines;
- The reasonableness of the assessments in the testing of students for the correspondence of residual knowledge to the declared competencies during the accreditation procedure of the university or institute.

The main interfaces shown in the figures show the capabilities of the MATRIX IC.

Work with the system begins with the login to the system. Teacher for work in the "Matrix" must register in the department of information systems of the University and get a login and password for logging in (authorization process). After entering the system, the teacher enters the menu shown in figure 1.

Figure 1: Menu "matrix."

For the teacher and students, it is important to assess the knowledge with the help of a rating-rating system. As we have said above, all student work and students' knowledge are evaluated at all stages of the educational process: attending lectures, working during practical and laboratory classes, performing independent works and projects, etc. An important stage is the control points for certain sections of the discipline, which represent an intermediate certification. Figure 2 shows the menu, which shows all the disciplines and groups in which the teacher is conducting the lessons[11,12]. Each discipline is associated with a particular group or groups. After entering this menu, there is an immediate opportunity to enter information on a group of students on the days when one or another type of training took place. Figure № 3 shows that all types of classes are taken into account: lectures, practical classes, laboratory works and control points for certain sections of the academic discipline. Presence and work on lectures are counted as "was-nebyl"; work in practical classes is taken into account on a five-point system of assessments, intermediate certification (control points) is taken into account on the scored points from 11-satisfactory. up to 20-excellent.

Figure 2: The rating system

#	Дата	Тип занятия	Внести результаты	Список
250469	06.09.2017	Практическое (лабораторное) занятие	Внести результаты	Список
250455	07.09.2017	Лекция	Внести результаты	Список
250456	14.09.2017	Лекция	Внести результаты	Список
255345	19.09.2017	Практическое (лабораторное) занятие	Внести результаты	Список
250477	28.09.2017	Классификация Информационных систем	Внести результаты	Список
250458	05.10.2017	Лекция	Внести результаты	Список
250471	11.10.2017	Практическое (лабораторное) занятие	Внести результаты	Список
250459	12.10.2017	Лекция	Внести результаты	Список
250472	25.10.2017	Практическое (лабораторное) занятие	Внести результаты	Список
250460	26.10.2017	Лекция	Внести результаты	Список
250478	26.10.2017	Характеристики и параметры элементов информационных систем	Внести результаты	Список
250461	02.11.2017	Лекция	Внести результаты	Список
250473	08.11.2017	Практическое (лабораторное) занятие	Внести результаты	Список
250462	09.11.2017	Лекция	Внести результаты	Список

Figure 3: Form for entering the results of students' work for all types of activities

As a result, during the academic semester, the student picks up a certain number of points. For admission to the exam, you need to score 55 points. The maximum score (100 points) can be typed by the student himself or received on the exam, taking into account the points that the teacher can put during the exam. At any time during the semester, the student can see the result of his work in the matrix (Figure 4). At the end of the semester, the resultant student progress sheet appears on the discipline: figure 5. Which shows how many points each student has scored during the semester. In figure № 6. A list with recommended grades for all students who were admitted before the exam is shown. From this list it can be seen that some students have already scored such a number of points, which corresponds to an excellent rating and such students can be boldly posed as "automatic", because the result of their work during the semester, intermediate certifications convincingly show their conscientious work and quite worthy knowledge.

Figure 4: Results of intermediate certification (control point No. 4.)

Figure 5: Progress in the discipline "IP Architecture" of the group DTSISB 2-1

Матрица.МГУП

• Вес экзамена, заданный преподавателем: 50%
• При расчёте итоговой оценки по дисциплине будет использована формула:

50 x Баллы за семестр + 50 x Баллы за экзамен

#	Имя	Нужно набрать на экзамене в баллах (по данным на 21.02.2018)			
		Отлично	Хорошо	Удовл.	Неуд.
27522	Цагареишвили София Георгиевна	85 — 100	55 — 84	—	0 — 54
27545	Смирнова Мария Алексеевна	85 — 100	55 — 84	—	0 — 54
27365	Солдатенков Максим Игоревич	87 — 100	57 — 86	55 — 56	0 — 54
27537	Сокольников Данила Александрович	91 — 100	61 — 90	55 — 60	0 — 54
27528	Мурдашева Надежда Ильдаровна	91 — 100	61 — 90	55 — 60	0 — 54
27542	Русин Тимофей Андреевич	97 — 100	67 — 96	55 — 66	0 — 54
27548	Гуляева Виктория Сергеевна	97 — 100	67 — 96	55 — 66	0 — 54
27563	Бирин Анастасия Витальевна	99 — 100	69 — 98	55 — 68	0 — 54
27558	Волосарь Дмитрий Максимович	100 — 100	70 — 99	55 — 69	0 — 54

Figure 6: Statement of achievement with the recommended estimates

2. Conclusions

Experience in operating the matrix information system shows that both students and teachers positively assessed the introduction of this information system in the educational process. Students have the opportunity in real time to observe their progress in learning and draw the appropriate conclusions. For teachers, working with this information system is an additional burden and it takes time to enter data, to account for the work of students at all stages of the learning process. However, we state that the introduction of this information system or similar motivates students to actively work at all stages of the educational process. As a result, students take exams in disciplines, where this system is introduced to higher grades and this improves the quality of training and promotes mastering all the declared competencies.

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